

Entrepreneurship Skills in Textile Printing for Women to Boost Family Income and Financial Sustainability

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Abstract

This paper looked at entrepreneurial skills in textile printing for women to acquire and boost family income and financial sustainability. Textile printing business is a viable form of enterprise that can be practiced at home and upscale to a bigger industrial venture if the right skills, techniques, and appropriate tools are used. This paper reviews entrepreneurship skills in textile printing. It reviewed the technicality involved in textile printing business and the concepts of entrepreneurship as it affects women in Nigeria. This paper will examine women entrepreneurs with their multiple roles in the family and as also working as entrepreneurs to boost family income and has shown different skills and methods in textile printing as a marketable skill for financial sustainability. The paper concludes by emphasizing the benefit of the textile printing as a boost to the family income especially at a time of economic challenges at the family and national levels. Recommendations are made on the need for Home Economists to provide training through formal and informal packages for women and youths to acquire textile printing skills, patronage by institutions and the government of these products should be encouraged and the need for startup loans to be provided by government for women and youths to upscale the textile printing businesses.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Skills, Financial sustainability, Textile printing and Family income

Introduction

In a world where it is becoming increasingly difficult for family to keep afloat of the impact of a progressively volatile economy, it makes economic sense for efforts to be geared towards cushioning the effect of the resulting hardship. The way such economic energies are directed is derivative from the inherent sustainable practice deducible from the knowledge already acquired by individual members of the family. That a family is experienced in any productive business or the art of Textile design business, is not enough motive to be complacent that food is sure on the table. Family sustenance, is the creative impetus that is injected to whatever economic practice that a family is engaged in.

One of the many ways a family can deplete the scourge of a family economic burden in the quest to boosting its income is reliant on the entrepreneurial drive that the family can infuse into its practice. The reason for an unwavering entrepreneurial tactics can be promoted to boost family economic capability. This is because the world today demands an aggressive entrepreneurial tactics to keep in tune with the trend of sustainability. D'orville, (2019) describes the world as being in an unsustainable track and this puts the living conditions and livelihoods, including family lives under stress. To confront that unstable economic situation, there is need for family financial sustainable.

To sustain and boost the income of a family is a condition that calls for the general concerns of all the components in the family. The role of women in the structure of

the family makes it more critical in boosting of family income. While playing several roles in the larger society as an indispensable character and at the macro level of the small family unit as a care giver, the remarkable responsibilities of women as the driving force for the economic well-being of families play a key role in the socio-economic development of the society at large. Entrepreneurship skills is a practice of production or of offering services that brings additional income, it encompasses the ability to set up and manage business in a way that will be profitable, Oshagbemi (2013), describes an entrepreneur as one who undertakes the risk of investing, creating, and funding an establishment with the intent to reaping the fruits of labor in terms of material and monetary gain.

The indispensable purpose of the family as a unity of the society is so deep-seated and relies on the change in status of domestic chores that now puts women on a platform of a larger role, this has broken the yoke that tied women's exploit only to the precinct of the kitchen alone as mere home keepers. Ibrahim (2008) states that the transition to current industrial society broke the shackles of restriction which secluded women before now as child minders; and so women are more prominent in the formal labor force. The status of women is enhanced when they engage in entrepreneurship activities. With the attending level of independence, there is also the enhancement of self-esteem to actively participate in household and community decision making processes.

Clothing and textiles offer a variety of skills which can be undertaken to boost family income. It is less demanding as women can take up an aspect of printing on textiles as an entrepreneurial venture to boost family income. Howard, Allan and Donald (2018) describes entrepreneurship as a dynamic process of creating wealth, it is just right that women benefit from textile printing as a means of boosting family income. Odeigha (2012) describes entrepreneurship as a dynamic process of creating wealth by individuals who take the major risks in terms of providing value to

products and services, the resulting products or services which may not be new but must be infused with value by the entrepreneur who has the necessary skill to create a novel output. As revealed by Success, Onubuogu, and Nwosu, (2015), an entrepreneur, is an innovator who recognizes and seizes opportunities and converts those opportunities into workable ideas, adds value, effort, money, skill and assumes risks of competition to actualize the ideas to get the reward.

The world is on an unstable track and so creativity, ingenuity, innovation, and imagination are known to play important roles in the development process of entrepreneurial skills, Akin-Fadeyi (2018). The gamut of the entire products of the textile industry is anchored on the precinct of functionality and fashion and fashion is reliant on the nurture provided by creativity, be it a large-scale outfit or a small-scale industry. Creativity is seen as the basis of survival of an entrepreneurial drive. Like a trio of a vehicle with twin engines, creative production must be combined with business knowledge and skills. Women have been engaged in this for ages, especially as shown in the various household chores they engaged in. As front runners in the spheres of income generation, Elebute and Ese, (2016), revealed that women are the main basket weavers within the context of Africa profession, that means women's efforts at enhancing family income is not a story of recent practice. In the areas of fabric or textile trade women are the basic traders in most African societies (Orga, 2017). Clothes are mostly woven by women in Northern and South West regions of Nigeria, clothes are hand-woven and highly dominated by the women folk, (Iriwieri, 2009),

The development of entrepreneurial skills by women can take two tracks. The first is to amend the social, economic, political, and cultural framework that hinder and foster those that stimulate their development. Secondly, it is an encouragement of women through their personalities and capabilities to enkindle the development of entrepreneurship. The

improvement of entrepreneurship is an instrument for improving the quality of life for families and communities and sustaining a better economy and environment. Halkias, Success, Harkiolakis and Caracatsanis (2011) discovered that female entrepreneurship in Nigeria is driven by micro-financing as well as family dynamics that work to shape and influence the birth of a business. Though women may be facing some limitations (Success, Harkiolakis and Caracatsanis, 2011), women entrepreneurs suffer from a set of diverse constraints like financial or credit constraints in financial institutions. Ikebuaku and Dinbabo (2018) observes that more than 50% of the women entrepreneurs used their capital or are dependent on their spouse or family members to start their businesses. As obligatory, running ones' business requires an enormous investment of time and resources.

This paper will examine women entrepreneurs with their multiple roles in the family and as also working as entrepreneurs to boost family income and has shown different skills and methods in textile printing as a marketable skill for financial sustainability. Discussion will be made on this premise.

Textile Printing Skills for Women's Entrepreneur to Boost Family Income

For ease of business and flexibility, Adetiloye (2020), hints on the pleasant opportunities that abound in establishing a small-scale printing outfit. In furtherance of this, there are aspects of hand printing techniques that can, as well, be adopted as business with equal financial benefits. That such entrepreneurship outfit can be domiciled at the homestead makes it a conviction that it can be adopted as a technique for direct hand printing business by women to boost family income. Printing is an age-long skill-oriented profession, printing is a method of design replication transfer from a template on to any surface called the substrate. The transfer may be by several means include the use of inks or colourants, pressure and other push-through tools. For printing on textiles,

is simply making patterns on fabric by colour application.

There are four approaches to printing on textiles, Britanical (2020) identifies block print, roller print, screen printing and heat transfer method, basically these four methods are classified into two forms of printing approaches: the industrial machine prints and the manual handprints which can be home-based. The industrial based printing is a scheme involving a whole lot of machineries, though it has been the hub of the printing business in Nigeria, but that is on the industrial scale and far from the desirable model of entrepreneurial practice that is suited for macro unit businesses at family level. For the reasons of huge cost implication at startups, attempt to boost family income is better approached from small mini-scale basis which can be scale up as the business improves, (Adetiloye, 2020). The accruing benefits from hand printing method as an entrepreneurship is that such an outfit can be simple to set up, it offers less financial burden and many of the inputs can be sourced locally.

The manual hand printing method can be adopted by women to increase ways of producing fabric design in beautiful ways, especially since textiles decoration can be printed on to the fabrics directly, Ashitey (2013) states that printing designs directly from leaves, weeds, twigs, traditional sponge and thread provided a collection of unique designs with aesthetic values. Varieties of designs and patterns that can be produced and sampled by manual printing approach on textile is a boost for textile printing entrepreneurship, there are different methods of textile printing.

Hand Printing Method Textile Printing

The method of textile hand printing is a myriad of techniques of physically infusing the pattern to the fabric by either hand pressing, stamping, rolling the design over the fabric, stenciling, or by screen printing. Aside from stenciling and screen printing which are mostly templates of voided designs to pass colors through, the others printing techniques rely solely on undulating

impressions in form of relief or intaglio which are inked and pressed onto the textile fabrics to print the designs. These may be made of wood as printing blocks or hand-held rollers (Britannica, 2020). Women are best suited for this business owing to their prowess at finger dexterity and the fact that women are at the front runners of fashion appreciation and are naturally aesthetics in appreciating beautiful articles.

Screen Printing and Stenciling

Screen printing and stenciling are two methods connected by their employment of voids through which inks are passed onto the fabric. Both methods are not laborious and can easily be undertaken by women to shore up family income. With stenciling, the designs are cut out of a sturdy paper for repeat use, while screen printing employs mesh where ink is forced through the openings and the non-printing areas are covered by the stencil which blocks the ink from passing through to the substrate. The open voids, as designs, are created on silk stretched over a frame, the frame of the silk or the paper template for stenciling are laid on the fabric to create the design and paint is push through the voids with either a brush, foam or a rubber called squeegee. For both methods, Storey, (1992), revealed that screen printing is an extension of stenciling. Screen printing can be made unique by making it an addition appendage printing on an existing fabric design as shown on (Fig 1)

Fig 1: Screen printing on existing design; photo source: C. M. Ojo.

As a design on already printed designs, screen printing designs can be specially projected to be added on to an existing design with the intent of adding value to the design or constricting the design to be personalized. The new intended design can be specially targeted for inclusion on the existing design by placing in open areas of floral or motifs or patterns. To break even in the quest for boosting family income, accurate multicolor printing can be enabled by further improvements of the screens using silk, cotton, viscose rayon, and cellulose diacetate, this ensures stable screens with non-water-based print pastes. In addition, hydrophobic synthetic materials, such as nylon and polyester, in combination with metal frames instead of wooden ones can be introduced. This will allow greater tension of the fabric when stretched over the frame, ensuring constant tension during the printing. Further still, improvements can be made in dryers, Ultraviolet curable inks may be introduced, which popularized screen printing technique even more. All these are to give allowances for a wider range of inks and dyes to be used in the screen printing.

Unconventional printing by Stamping

An array of creative designs can be fashioned with several objects reclaimed from the environment, the non-replicable nature of such objects on prints makes for the uniqueness of the designs in their demand. With simple handprints made by stamping, rolling, or pressing, women entrepreneurs can have the merit of saving cost in production by adopting unconventional objects as pattern templates, some of these unconventional objects include leaf, metals, plastics, tree backs, broken parts of machine, wood grains, used tyres, soles of shoes and any of such in the environment, some of which are presented as fig.2.

Fig 2: Odds objects that can be adoptable for textile printing; source: A. A. Yusuf

Textile fabrics can be printed directly by coloring the relief design and stamping, rolling, or pressing against the fabric. An all-over pattern arranged in special format may be achieved, better still, the stamping or pressing may be randomly done with the intent of making an abstract print or designed to likeness. The little ways in which textile printing can be made at home at the micro-system level using the little things that can be found in the environment shows that family financial sustainability can be achieved especially in terms of resource conservation.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Without recourse to the prevailing market condition, having skills in textile printing stemming from the family stead will be a new wave to boost family income. Whether as infusion pattern on post factory-flora-prints or added as motif enhancement or a new contorted pattern printed on a plain fabric, the possibilities of textile printing are limitless as to the array of viable printed textile patterns that can be instituted at family level to boost income. From already made T-shirt to sewn dresses or plain fabrics, textile printing at home is possible. Based on the discussion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Practical aspect of Clothing and textiles production can be organized by Home Economists for women and youths both formally and informally to inculcate textile printing skills through organized practical workshops.
2. Startup businesses such as textile printing can be a mini scale business to arrest unemployment, therefore, government should provide start up

- loans and funds to support handmade textile printed fabrics.
3. Industries, market forces, institutions and government can patronize products from small scale mini businesses to encourage and to provide the income that is being pursued by women at the family level.

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